

MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES ARE INVOLVED IN TEACHING ENGLISH TODAY

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ABSTRACT.

This article discusses the role of modern interactive methods and innovative technologies in teaching English today, as well as several methods of effective teaching of English, and the role of modern methods or modern educational technologies used in language and its study.

Keywords: multimedia, pedagogical technology, information technology, foreign language, IELTS, directions, methods, direct method, language, grammar translation, audio-visual method, interest, activity, interactive methods.

Introduction. Given the increasing importance of English as a leading means of international communication in the world and the absence of serious tendencies to stop or slow down this process, the problem of using effective methods in this regard is posed. In the modern sense, the educational process is considered as a process of interaction between teachers and students in order to familiarize students with certain knowledge, skills, abilities and values. Thus, the use of modern information technology tools and methods in the educational process of students in various disciplines allows teachers, first of all, to improve their knowledge and skills in this area, to provide the education system with technical support, and to fully use educational and methodological knowledge. Today, the main attention is paid to the student, his personality and his unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organizing educational activities of students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been increasingly raised. This is

not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practically master a foreign language.

In the research process, popular methods of teaching and learning English, Internet resources were used. During the writing of the article, the principles of theoretical-deductive inference, analysis and synthesis, and logic were used.

The teacher's task is to create conditions for the practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The teacher's task is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as cooperative learning, project methodology, the use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the learning process, ensure individualization and differentiation of teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning. Forms of working with computer teaching programs in foreign language lessons include: learning vocabulary; practicing pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; developing grammatical phenomena. The possibilities of using Internet resources are enormous. The global Internet creates conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to obtain any necessary information: regional geographical materials, news from the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

In English lessons, a number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet: the formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing skills of schoolchildren; replenishing students' vocabulary; forming students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at exploring the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the horizons of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relations and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in tests, quizzes, competitions, Olympiads held on the Internet, participate in correspondence with peers in other countries, conversations, video conferences, etc. Students can get information about the problem they are currently working on in the project. The substantive foundations of mass computerization are connected with the fact that a modern computer

is an effective means of optimizing the conditions of mental labor, in general, any of its manifestations. The computer has one characteristic that is determined when it is used as a tool for teaching others and as an assistant in acquiring knowledge, which is its inanimate nature. The machine can be in a "friendly" relationship with the user and at times "support" him, but it never shows signs of irritation and does not allow you to feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are realized in the process of implementing this main goal. The communicative approach involves teaching communication and the formation of the ability to interact intercultural, which is the basis of Internet activity. The Internet has no meaning outside of communication - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, the life of which is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the largest conversation in terms of the number and volume of participants that has ever taken place. By participating in a lesson in a foreign language, we create a real model of communication.

Currently, priority is given to the issues of communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in a cultural context, autonomy of education and humanism. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of foreign language teaching is to teach free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond in various situations, i.e. communication. Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (this is the so-called principle of communicative authenticity). New technologies, in particular the Internet, are trying to correct this error. The communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication, aimed at consciously perceiving the material and working with it, creating psychological and linguistic readiness for communication. Implementing a communicative approach on the Internet is not particularly difficult for the user. The communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows us to distinguish this approach from other types of educational

activities is that students independently select linguistic units to form their own opinions. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its goal is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is the creation of interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "the unification, coordination and complementation of efforts in the communicative goal and result using speech tools". By teaching a real language, the Internet helps to form speech abilities and skills, and also ensures sincere interest in teaching vocabulary and grammar, and therefore efficiency. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond to them adequately in a foreign language. One of the technologies that provide student-centered learning is the project method as a way to develop creativity, cognitive activity and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprospects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In real practice, it is often necessary to deal with mixed projects, which include research projects, creative, practice-oriented and informative features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate fosters moral values such as mutual assistance and empathy, forms creativity and activates students. In general, in the process of project learning, the inseparability of teaching and upbringing is observed.

The project method develops students' communication skills, communication culture, the ability to concisely and easily formulate thoughts, tolerance for the opinions of communication partners, the ability to receive information from various sources, processes it using modern computer technologies, creates a language environment that contributes to the emergence of a natural need. in communication in a foreign language. The project form of work is one of the most relevant technologies that allows students to apply the knowledge gained on the subject. Students expand their horizons, the boundaries of language knowledge, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, understand each other when defending projects. Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, thereby creating the

opportunity for direct contact with a real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of a textbook. Project work is a creative process. The student independently or under the guidance of a teacher seeks a solution to the problem, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of subject knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual skills. In the process of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the framework of program materials on almost any subject. Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities. TO modern technologies, collaborative technology is also applicable. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various learning environments. Children are grouped into groups of 3-4 people, they are given one task, while the role of each is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the entire group. Therefore, weak students try to figure out what they do not understand from what is not strong, and strong students strive to help the weak understand the task thoroughly. And the whole class benefits from this, because the gaps are closed together.

In conclusion, the introduction of information technologies into education significantly diversifies the process of perceiving and processing information. Thanks to computers, the Internet and multimedia, students have a unique opportunity to assimilate a large amount of information with subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding significantly. In the conditions of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, conduct interviews and hold teleconferences themselves. The main criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of a foreign language in language portfolio technology are tests. The priority of this technology is to redirect the educational process from the teacher to the student. The student, in turn, is consciously responsible for the results of his cognitive activity. The above technology leads to the gradual formation of students' skills in independently assimilating information. In general, the language portfolio is multifunctional and contributes to the development of multilingualism.

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